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THEOGENESIAL THEORY AND DARWINISM: A BIBLICAL CLARIFICATION ON THE ORIGIN OF THE UNIVERSE

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Abstract

The main aim of this paper is to demystify biblical cosmogony through *Theogenesial Theory* as against Darwinism and subsequently elucidate the trichotomous nature of man created by God in His image (Imago Dei). The *Theogenesial Theory* states that everything came into existence by divine fiat, both the physical and non-physical elements. This theory posits that God is the Source and Beginning of all things—living and non-living things. He created all things. In other words, the universe came into existence as a result of divine fiat. God created the universe through His creative Word by fiat. Life originated through divine creation or divine intelligent design, and not through abiogenesis. All species were created by God, a living Spirit. Theogenesis, according to the Bible, accentuates that God created the universe in six days and rested on the seventh day by speaking it (the universe) into existence. Adopting solus primus scriptura research (SPSR) and a biblical descriptive model, the author develops a Demarcation Standard for Truth (DSI) and concludes that Darwinism, or Charles Darwin's Theory of Evolution, and its associated Big Bang Theory contradict biblical cosmogony.

Keywords: theogenesial theory, big bang theory, darwinism, origin of the cosmos (universe), tripartite nature of man, cosmogony, science.

Introduction

There has been a kind of intellectual rigidity imposed on the origin of cosmic discourse, especially from the scientific angle, perhaps arising from a lack of fossil evidence to support their claims to valid knowledge. The answer is not far-fetched. The origin of the cosmos (universe) transcends secular science and philosophy. It is within the purview of biblical theology. Biblical cosmogenesis¹ explains how God created the cosmos (universe) in six days (Gen 1:1-31)²; gives a graphic explanation of how Adam's creation was done (Gen 2:4-25); proves God's creative power (Ps 104); and evinces God's wisdom role in creation generally (Prov 8:22-31). This is the exact import of Theogenesis or Theogenesial Theory³ that God, as a Creator, created the entire universe (Genesis 1:1) *ex nihilo*⁴ (from or out of nothing); designed the universe intelligently and purposefully in six days (Gen 1:3-31); and created man in His image – Imago Dei (Gen 1:26-27, 2:7). The biblical cosmogenesis and theogenesis are in contrast to the big bang theory that depicts the universe arising from a heat at a point that culminated into a sudden explosion, and Darwinism, which refers to the scientific theory of evolution through natural selection. Indeed, according to the Bible, “Through faith we understand that the worlds were framed (created) by the word of God, so that things which are seen were not made of things which do appear” (Heb 11:3). God created the universe through His creative Word by fiat: “And God said Let there be ...” and it was so (Gen 1: 3, 6, 9, 11, 14, 20, 24, 26; Ps 33:6-9; Heb 11:3).

Thus far, Charles Darwin and his intellectual descendants are unable to explain the emergence of the phenomenon of life. It is only an intelligent God who created the heaven and the earth who has the adequate, appropriate palette and paints to generate such a masterpiece⁵. In his words, James P. Gills (2002) says, “The only explanation for both elm and elk is in design, an intelligent design, a design shrouded in mysterious beauty and predicated on a purpose.” He stresses that, in the face of physical evidence available, Darwinism is untenable. He goes further to aver that the *microevolution*, the miniature alterations that permit one individual to be born more capable than its siblings or enable a bacterium to survive a pharmacological assault, can be readily observed in the field. Nevertheless, Gills says the convincing evidence of *macroevolution*, that is, “the emergence of entirely novel creatures and life itself through a mechanism of random mutation,” is completely absent in the fossil evidence, embryology, and microbiology. What is more, mathematical probabilities completely rule out chance as the mediating factor in the appearance and diversification of life. In light of this, Gills characterises Darwinism as a “myth” that science is yet to buttress sufficiently to win the gamble on the theory’s explanatory and predictive powers.

Therefore, the paper aims to demystify biblical cosmogony through *Theogenesial Theory* as against Darwinism and subsequently elucidates the trichotomous nature of man created by God in His image (Imago Dei). The author adopts solus primus scriptura research (SPSR) and a biblical descriptive model, developing a Demarcation Standard for Truth (DST) and concludes that Darwinism or Charles Darwin’s Theory of Evolution and its associated Big Bang Theory⁶

¹ Biblical cosmogenesis refers to the biblical account of the origin and creation of the universe.

² All biblical quotations in this work are from the King James Version except otherwise indicated

³ Theogenesial Theory says that God is the origin and creator of the universe developed by this author to explain the origin of the universe.

⁴ *Ex nihilo* is the doctrine of creation that maintains that matter is not eternal and that no matter existed prior to the divine creative act at the initial moment of the cosmic process.

⁵ Gills, James P. “Conclusion” in Gills, James P., et.al. (eds.). *Darwinism under the microscope*. Charisma House, 2002.

⁶ Big Bang Theory developed by Georges Lemaître, a Belgian cosmologist and Catholic priest in 1931. For a better understanding, see Ilesanmi, “Pneumagenesial Theory: The Groundwork for a Biblical Understanding of the Origin of the Cosmos” in *Mature Journal of the International Institute of Christian theologians, Scholars, and Professionals*, Vol. 2(3), 2024

contradict biblical cosmogony. The biblical creation theories can be approached in three connected paradigms but one way. That is, the three paradigms approach biblical creation in diverse ways but point to one source of creation—God. This is called by this author: “*One-three fold Theory of Creation*”.

Figure 1: *Biblical/ Divine Creation Theories developed by D. A. Ilesanmi: 2024*

Figure 2: *Biblical/ Divine Creation Theories developed by D. A. Ilesanmi: 2024.*

Theogenesial Theory

Theogenesial theory asserts that a Supreme Being, God, initiated creation through divine will. The creation of the universe, of which man is a part, cannot be fully grappled and understood through modern scientific perspectives that tend to emphasise naturalistic explanations grounded in empirical evidence without pneumatic revelation. This is the argument of theopneumagenesial or pneumagenesial theory propounded by Dele Alaba Ilesanmi (2024) in his work titled *Pneumagenesial Theory: The Groundwork for a Biblical Understanding of the Origin of the Cosmos*. He unveils the origin of the universe through a biblical lens as opposed to the big bang theory's claim. Ilesanmi argues that the creation of the cosmos or universe is not within the purview of secular philosophy and science, but a metaphysical theology and spiritual cosmology (spiritual metaphysics). That the universe, as an orderly system, was intelligently designed by a transcendental invisible Being (God). He asserts that everything that exists in the physical and non-physical realm has its spiritual metaphysical determinant that controls it. This is the major import of Ilesanmi's Pneumagenesial Theory in order to have a better grip on the cosmosophy.⁷

The Big Bang Theory is believed to be a dominant paradigm within astrophysics. It postulates that approximately 13.8 billion years ago, all matter was condensed into an infinitely dense singularity before expanding rapidly. This sudden explosion of the condensed matter lacks scientific or archaeological evidence. In addition, the question of how matter came to be has not been addressed by the proponents of this theory. What is more, the role of God in creation is not only completely downplayed in this theory but absolutely ruled out. The Big Bang theory lacks epistemological validity—that is, the knowledge claim here cannot be regarded as knowledge because it lacks truth, reliability, and objectivity. The theory is a mere dream in the mind or the hallucination of the proponent.

However, theogenesial theory argues that science alone cannot encapsulate human experience or explain why there is something rather than nothing—a question that philosophy grapples with extensively. They contend that understanding our universe requires acknowledging dimensions beyond physical laws—moral truths, consciousness, and aesthetic experiences—which may be indicative of a higher intelligence or divine design. Thus, *Theogenesial Theory* states that everything came into existence by divine fiat⁸, both the physical and non-physical elements⁹. This theory posits that God is the Source and Beginning of all things—living and non-living things. He created all things (Gen 1:1-31) and no one created Him. Everything has its source and end in God that has no source and end. In other words, the universe came into existence as a result of divine fiat. God created the universe through His creative Word by fiat: “And God said Let there be ...” and it was so (Gen 1: 3, 6, 9, 11, 14, 20, 24, 26; Ps 33:6-9; Heb 11:3). Life originated through divine creation or intelligent design, and not through abiogenesis. All species were created by God, a living Spirit. Theogenesis, according to the Bible, accentuates that God created the universe in six days and rested the seventh day by spoken it (the universe) into existence.

Six days of Creation: Genesis 1:3–2:3

⁷ Cosmosophy is defined as knowledge or understanding of the cosmos (universe). It is a term formed by combining "cosmo-" referring to the universe and "-sophy" meaning wisdom or knowledge.

⁸ “Fiat” is a divine authoritative decree. The word comes from a Latin word with the same spelling as the English word, meaning “let there be.” In early Latin Bible translations, *fiat* appears six times in the first chapter of Genesis. Its first appearance is found in the phrase *fiat lux*, meaning “let there be light” (Gen 1:3). See <https://www.gotquestions.org/fiat-creationism.html> for better understanding.

⁹ “Element” here means everything in existence, visible and invisible.

The creative acts are arranged logically and systematically so that the first three days set up the environments necessary for the creations of the last three days to thrive. For example, God created light on the first day, and the light produced heavenly bodies on the fourth day; the sea, on the second day, produced birds and fishes on the fifth day; and land and plants were created on the third day to produce animals and human beings. Here is the orderly arrangement of the universe as created by God in the Book of Genesis, chapter one:

Days of Creation

Day 1	Light		Day 4	Celestial bodies, such as Sun, moon, and stars.
Day 2	Sea and Firmament		Day 5	Birds and Fish
Day 3	Land and Plants		Day 6	Land animals and humans

Each day follows a similar literary pattern:

Introduction: "And God said"

Command: "Let there be"

Report: "And it was so"

Evaluation: "And God saw that it was good"

Time sequence: "And there was evening, and there was morning"

Genesis 1:31 sums up all of creation with an evaluative summary: "And God saw everything that he had made, and, behold, it was very good. And the evening and the morning were the sixth day." According to R. N. Whybray, a biblical scholar, "This is the craftsman's assessment of his own work ... It does not necessarily have an ethical connotation: it is not mankind that is said to be 'good', but God's work as craftsman."¹⁰ Indeed, the biblical cosmogony as encapsulated in Genesis chapter one above gives the most logical, sensible, and valid explanation of the cosmic origin. This has not been disproved by true science, and many fine and brilliant scientists have believed this creation account, and it is God's revelation that is beyond human speculation.

¹⁰ See https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Genesis_creation_narrative

Theogenesial /Creation Sequence

Figure 3: Theogenesial/creation Sequence.

Principles Underlying Theogenesial Theory

Principles are basic truths that guide our actions. A principle is an explanation of the fundamental reasons why things are the way they are¹¹. When one knows the principles underlying a theory, one will understand it better. That of *Theogenesis* or *Theogenesial Theory* is not different. The following are the fundamental principles of the theory, which are the same as the principles underlying pneumagenesis:

1. God is the source and beginning of all creation – all which exists.
2. Everything in existence or that God created, physical and nonphysical, has its root in the spirit realm (Gen 1:1-31). In other words, everything that exists in the physical world has its basis in the spiritual world.
3. Revelation and creation are pneumatical (spiritual) and only those that are pneumatically¹² or theopneumatically¹³ (spiritually) alive can unravel the mysteries of God, in which the origin of the universe is among (1Cor 2:10-11)
4. God is the root of all things (Gen 1:1-31)

¹¹ Heward-Mills, Dag. Seven Great Principles. Parchment House, 2000. P.92

¹² “Pneumatically” means “spiritually”

¹³ “Theopneumatically” means “having God’s Spirit” or simply, “spiritually”

5. God is a Spirit (John 4:24) who controls all things He created.
6. God created the cosmos or the universe and still providentially controls it.
7. Everything God created has its origin in creation and the spirit of God was involved in the genesis or beginning of all creation (Gen 1:1-2).
8. Reality extends beyond mere physical existence, but superphysical reality is behind every existence.
9. God controls everything He created spiritually because He is the Father of spirits (Heb 29:9) and the Lord of hosts (1Sam 1:3; 4:4; Ps 24:10; Rom 9:29; James 5:4; etc). and all things are theopneumatically created.
10. Behind the physical world, there is an invisible, supernatural force or power that controls it.
11. There are three realities about this present universe (cosmos): 1. God created it; 2. God controls it; and 3. God will still end it.
12. Pneumagogy¹⁴ is the only tool we can employ to understand the spiritual realities of life. It is practically impossible to explain spiritual realities with spirit-taught words to a man that is bereft of theopneuma without the involvement of the Holy Spirit.

Darwinism

In recent times, Darwinism, or Charles Darwin's evolutionary theory of the origin of man, has been regarded as more of a mere wishful thinking than fact. One of the woes of Darwinism is fossil¹⁵ problem. Unfortunately, Darwin's theory keeps going like "the bunny in the Energizer battery commercials."¹⁶ Darwinism, also known as the Darwinian Theory, refers to the scientific theory of evolution through natural selection, proposed by Charles Darwin in his 1859 book, *On the Origin of Species*. The theory states that all living organisms evolve over time through the process of variation, mutation, genetic drift, and gene flow, with the primary driving force being natural selection. Charles Darwin explains how species evolve over generations through natural selection and the inheritance of physical or behavioural traits. It emphasises the gradual change of organisms and the diversity of life on Earth.

¹⁴ "pneumagogy" is the science and art of teaching and learning under the leadership of the Holy Spirit. For a better understanding of this concept, see Ilesanmi, Dele A, "Pneumagogy: A Proposed Theory for Effective Teaching and Learning in Christian Kingdom Education" in *African Journal of Kingdom Education*, 2023.

¹⁵ "Fossil" is any preserved remains, impression, or trace of any once-living thing from a past geological age. See <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fossil> for a better understanding.

¹⁶ Hartwig, Mark. "Challenging Darwin' Myths" in Gills, James P., et.al. (eds.). *Darwinism under the microscope*. Charisma House, 2002. P.27

Figure 4. *Caricatures Of Charles Darwin with the body of an ape or monkey symbolised evolution (see <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Darwinism>)*

Figure 5: *Charles Darwin's Theory of Evolution*

Charles Darwin's Theory of Evolution explains how humans evolved from a common ancestor with other primates. Here's a simplified, step-by-step overview:

Stage 1: Emergence of Life (~3.5 billion years ago)

- Life emerged from non-living matter through abiogenesis.
- Simple organisms, such as single-celled bacteria, dominated the Earth.

Stage 2: Development of Complex Life (~2.1 billion years ago)

- Cells evolved into more complex forms, such as multicellular organisms.
- Photosynthesis and respiration developed.

Stage 3: Origin of Vertebrates (~530 million years ago)

- Vertebrates (animals with backbones) emerged.
- Early vertebrates were simple, fish-like creatures.

Stage 4: Tetrapods and Amphibians (~360 million years ago)

- Tetrapods (four-legged vertebrates) evolved.
- Amphibians developed, allowing for transition from water to land.

Stage 5: Reptiles and Mammals (~300 million years ago)

- Reptiles dominated the Earth.
- Mammals emerged as small, nocturnal creatures.

Stage 6: Primate Evolution (~65 million years ago)

- Primates evolved from small, nocturnal mammals.
- Early primates were similar to modern prosimians (lemurs, lorises).

Stage 7: Hominin Evolution (~6-8 million years ago)

- Hominins (human-like species) emerged.
- Early hominins, such as Sahelanthropus, walked upright.

Stage 8: Bipedalism (~4-6 million years ago)

- Bipedalism became more prominent.
- Species like *Ardipithecus ramidus* and *Australopithecus afarensis* appeared.

Stage 9: Homo Habilis (~2.8-1.4 million years ago)

- *Homo habilis* emerged, with more advanced tools.
- Brain size increased.

Stage 10: Homo Erectus (~1.8-70,000 years ago)

- *Homo erectus* migrated out of Africa.
- Controlled fire, hunting, and gathering developed.

Stage 11: Homo Sapiens (~200,000 years ago)

- *Homo sapiens* (modern humans) emerged in Africa.
- Brain size increased, and cognitive abilities developed.

Stage 12: Human Migration and Diversification (~60,000 years ago)

- Humans migrated out of Africa.
- Populations adapted to various environments.

As evolution became widely accepted in the 1870s,

These are the basic tenets of evolution by natural selection as defined by Darwin¹⁷:

1. More individuals are produced each generation than can survive.
2. Phenotypic variation exists among individuals and the variation is heritable.
3. Those individuals with heritable traits better suited to the environment will survive.
4. When reproductive isolation occurs new species will form.

Here are some problems and criticisms of Darwinism:

Scientific Criticisms:

1. Lack of Transitional Fossils: Insufficient fossil record evidence for gradual transitions between species.
2. Irreducible Complexity: Complex biological systems difficult to explain through gradual evolution.
3. Origin of Life: Uncertainty surrounding life's origin and abiogenesis.
4. Genetic Limitations: Genetic mutations and variations may not suffice for macroevolution.
5. Non-Random Mutations: Mutations may not occur randomly, challenging natural selection.

Philosophical and Theological Criticisms:

1. Purpose and Meaning: Darwinism implies lack of purpose or meaning in life.
2. Moral Relativism: Evolutionary ethics may lead to moral relativism.
3. Human Dignity: Reduces human value to biological processes.
4. Teleology: Difficulty explaining direction or purpose in evolution.
5. Theistic Evolution: Compatibility issues with traditional theism.

Logical and Methodological Criticisms:

1. Tautology: Survival of the fittest is a tautology (circular reasoning).
2. Lack of Predictive Power: Evolutionary theory struggles to make testable predictions.
3. Ad Hoc Hypotheses: Frequent introduction of ad hoc explanations.
4. Methodological Naturalism: Excludes supernatural explanations a priori.
5. Confirmation Bias: Selective interpretation of data to support evolution.

¹⁷ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Darwinism>

The Reality about God

In his work, *Does God Exist?* Ilesanmi (2020) asserts that “What to know about God has been made known to us already and this is very plain (Rom 1:19). Thus, whosoever denies the existence of God is only wilfully rejecting the truth that he knows. It means that such a person is a fool (Psalms 14:1; 53:1)”¹⁸.

Ilesanmi further stated that:

With the benefit of hindsight, to know that God exists is crystal clear. Indeed, the revelation of God to man does not completely exhaust His being and activity. Although to some He is arguably incomprehensible, no man can absolutely fathom Him (Deut 29:29; Job 36:26; Isa 40:28). He cannot be comprehended but can only be apprehended. Sancy says “Finitude cannot comprehend infinity [sic], nor human thought patterns, which are associated with the created environment, completely grasp the transcendent realm of God” (Horton, op. cit. pp 88). Robert says on the basis of this limitation of human reasoning, some strains of mystical theology have denied knowing God. For example, modern rationalism has argued for the “unknowability” of God. No wonder the fool denies the existence of God (Psalm 14:1)¹⁹.

According to Arlie J.H. cited by Lewis G.R. (2006), the priori approach argues that from a conception of God as being so perfect that His non-existence is inconceivable. He says that a posteriori approach gives evidence from the world, from the observable, empirical universe, insisting that God is necessary to explain certain features of the cosmos because He is the Creator. The last approach is the existential approach, which asserts that the direct experience of God is by way of personal revelation.²⁰ The truth of the matter is that God exists. Though we cannot fully understand Him, we understand that He created the universe. We cannot fully understand Him because it is impossible for the finitude to comprehend infinitude – man as finitude cannot fully understand God, the infinitude.

Demarcation Standard for Truth (DST)

The first point of wisdom is to know the truth, while the second is to discern what is false. For one to know the truth, therefore, one needs to be connected to the truth (Ps 31:5; John 14:6; 15:1-10). Ilesanmi (2024) sets a *Demarcation Standard for Truth* in his recent masterpiece titled *Biblical Research: A Theological and Epistemological Inquiry*, under a subheading, *What is Truth?* According to him, the Bible holds the truth of God because it is a revelation of Him (God) to humanity. Thus, finding the truth, he asserts that, biblical Christian educational research is required. Ilesanmi claims that the whole body of Biblical Christian educational theory rests on the recognition that all truth is of God the Father. He is the God of truth (Ps 31:5); God the Son, our Lord Jesus Christ, is the Lord of truth (John 14:6); and God the Holy Spirit, His Spirit is the Spirit of truth (John 14:16–17). “All truth, whether discerned or undiscerned by man, springs from a single source, the triune God and therefore consists as one harmonious whole”²¹. Ilesanmi avers that no concept can be

¹⁸ Ilesanmi, Dele A “Does God Exist? 2020 in Christopress. <https://www.christopress.com/does-god-exist/>

¹⁹ Ibid.

²⁰ Cited in Ilesanmi, Dele A “Does God Exist? 2020 in Christopress. <https://www.christopress.com/does-god-exist/>

²¹ Ilesanmi, Dele A. “Biblical Research: A Theological and Epistemological Inquiry” in *Mature Journal of the International Institute of Christian theologians, Scholars, and Professionals*, Vol. 2(2), 2024.

true that conflicts with the statements of the Scriptures. Equally, no untruth is a legitimate support of divine revelation or has any place in the ministry of spiritual truth. A genuine reverence for the God of truth compels a conscientious regard for accuracy in all areas of factual investigation and reporting. He argues further by asking a few important questions: “Where can we find what is considered as truth? Is it in the scientific inquiry or experimentation? Or in the philosophical inquiry and debate? Is it in the secular university or marketplace?” And he affirms that “The truth can be found in no other place than in the Word of God, the Bible.”. He posits that “The Bible is a corpus of truth and magazine of life; the Bible is the only repository of true knowledge and the only single source of truth. Any research found that cannot be established by the Word of God cannot be considered as truth”. Ilesanmi concludes his *Demarcation Standard for Truth* (DST) by saying that “In biblical educational research, the truth cannot be discovered through scientific or secular research but through the Holy Spirit, who is the Spirit of truth and who teaches truth and guides believers into all truth (John 16:13). Thus, truth is pneumagogical”²².

The concept of *Demarcation Standard for Truth* (DST) is the principles and criteria used to distinguish biblical knowledge from non-biblical knowledge to evaluate the truthfulness of claims. It is the criteria for evaluating all claims to truth. The standard-setting to distinguish truth from falsehood, to evaluate the accuracy of teachings, and all claims to truth.

Ilesanmi’s Demarcation Standard for Truth (IDST):

Before truth can be regarded as truth, it must not be incongruous with the following statements:

1. God is truth and the source of all truths
2. All truths must be traceable to God of truth
3. The word of God is truth (Ps 119:160; John 17:17)
4. The truth is absolute
5. No concept, theory or method can be true that conflicts with the statements of the Scriptures. That is, not contradictory to the word of God (Mat 7:12)
6. No untruth is a legitimate support of divine revelation
7. Every truth discovered must find its supportive evidence from the Scriptures.
8. Every theory or concept rests on the recognition that all truth is of God.
9. Truth is divine and revelatory
10. Truth can only be found in the word of God.
11. Truth cannot be discovered through scientific or secular lens but through the Holy Spirit, who is the Spirit of truth and who teaches truth and guides believers into all truth (John 16:13).
12. Science, logic, law, philosophy, theology, or any field of human learning is a means not an end to truth because revelation supersedes education, and truth is revelatory.
13. Truth is constant or invariable.
14. Truth is timeless.
15. Law of Excluded middle is not applicable (Mat 12:30)
16. It is absolute
17. It is objective
18. It is knowable
19. It is inerrant, infallible or reliable
20. It is valid and verifiable.
21. The Bible is the only repository of true knowledge and only single source of truth. In other words, truth is biblical or Scriptural

The Demarcation Standard can be subsumed under five key points.

²² Ibid.

Demarcation Standard for Truth

Figure 6: Demarcation Standard for Truth developed by D. A. Ilesanmi: 2024.

Truth is built on three criteria:

1. Sola Scriptura (Scripture alone)
2. Sola Christus (Christ alone)
3. Sola Fide (Faith alone)

Figure 7: Three criteria for Truth developed by D. A. Ilesanmi: 2024.

Biblical Clarification on the Creation of Man

The biblical account of the creation of man is lucid and unambiguous: “And God said, Let us make man in our image, after our likeness . . .” (Gen 1:26). “So God created man in his own image, in the image of God created he him; male and female created he them” (Gen 1:27; cf. 1Cor 15:45). God explains how this creation was done in Genesis 2:7: “And the LORD God formed man from the dust of the ground, and breathed into his nostrils the breath of life, and man became a living soul”. In other words, the Spirit of God imparted on the body of man to produce a living soul. This is the second account of God’s creation of man. It does not contradict the first account but gives added information to expatiate on Genesis 1:26-27. The Bible calls man “a living soul.” The breath of life became man's spirit; that is, the principle of life within him.”²³

What is more, the inbreathing of God produced a two-fold life: soulical and spiritual. In other words, the immaterial dimension in human nature is divided into two distinct and separate faculties: soul and spirit. “When the inbreathing of God entered man's body it became the spirit of man; but when the spirit reacted with the body the soul was produced. This explains the source of our spiritual and soulical lives. We must recognise, though, that this spirit is not God's own life...”²⁴ In Job 33:4 “The Spirit of God hath made me, and the breath of the Almighty hath given me life.” (cf. Gen 2:7; Job 27:3; 32:8; Ps 33:6). The spirit of man is different from the Holy Spirit. “Formed man of dust from the ground” refers to man's body; “breathed into his nostrils the breath of life” refers to man's spirit as it came from God; and “Man became a living soul” refers to man's soul when the body was quickened by the spirit and brought into being a living and self-conscious man²⁵. Without the spirit, the inbreathing of God, the body is dead, but with the spirit from God the body is made alive. Thus, the spirit of God was active in creative process right from Genesis 1 to 2. This is what Ilesanmi (2024) calls *pneumagenesis* or *theopneumagenesis*²⁶. Theopneumagenesial Theory states that everything that exists, visible and invisible, has its spiritual metaphysical determinant that controls it, and that spiritual metaphysical determinant is the Spirit of God, the Holy Spirit²⁷. The tripartite man can be partially explained thus:

This trinity of spirit, soul and body may be partially illustrated by a light bulb. Within the bulb, which can represent the total man, there are electricity, light and wire. The spirit is like the electricity, the soul the light, and body the wire. Electricity is the cause of the light while light is the effect of electricity. Wire is the material substance for carrying the electricity as well as for manifesting the light. The combination of spirit and body produces soul, that which is unique to man. As electricity, carried by the wire, is expressed in light, so spirit acts upon the soul and the soul, in turn, expresses itself through the body.²⁸

Furthermore, man’s body is composed of elements found on the earth (Gen 3:19). In the Hebrew language even the word for man, Adam (Gen 2: 20) is a biblical term that is connected to the

²³ Ilesanmi, Dele A. “Trichotomy vs Dichotomy: The Trinitarian Composition of Man” citing Watchman Nee: <http://articles.ochristian.com/article1935.shtml> Retrieved on 25/7/20 published in christopress, 2020.

²⁴ Ibid.

²⁵ Ibid.

²⁶ Ilesanmi, Dele A. “Pneumagenesial Theory: The Groundwork for a Biblical Understanding of the Origin of the Cosmos” in *Mature Journal of the International Institute of Christian theologians, Scholars, and Professionals*, Vol. 2(3), 2024

²⁷ Ibid. Ilesanmi, Dele A. 2024

²⁸ Op.cit. Ilesanmi, Dele A citing Watchman Nee in Christopress, 2020

Hebrew word *adamah* (אָדָמָה), which means *soil* or *earth*, suggesting that Adam was formed from the earth,²⁹ and in Yoruba word, it is called *amo* (clay), pointing to the same source: soil or earth. But man is not mere body, he is made of soul and spirit (Eccl 12:7; Ps 31:5; Acts 7:59; 2 Cor 5:6-8; 1 Thess 5:23; Heb 4:12; 12:22-23; Rev 6:9-11). In the creation of man's body, God used previously existing material (the dust of the ground) which He created before man. But we cannot say that He used previously existing materials when He brought plant and animal life into existence – He (God) commanded them into existence by fiat. We cannot say man came to be because of matter which condensed into an infinitely dense singularity before escalating rapidly as a result of heat or man evolves from lifeless matter into a living soul. This divine creation is contrary to big bang theory and Darwinism. What connects the earth (body) and living soul (man) is spiritual metaphysics (the spirit from God or the breath of God). It is practically impossible to produce life from non-living matter. Death occurs when there is a permanent separation between body, soul, and spirit (Eccl 12:7).

The theory that tries to explain the development of life on earth from lifeless matter to man, leaving God out of the creation of man is atheistic and the “scientific” theory of evolution through natural selection, proposed by Charles Darwin in his 1859 book titled "On the Origin of Species" is ungodly. The theory states that all living organisms evolve over time through the process of variation, mutation, genetic drift, and gene flow, with the primary driving force being natural selection. This is unscriptural. The Bible says, "And the LORD God formed man from the dust of the ground, and breathed into his nostrils the breath of life, and man became a living soul". It is not possible for life to come from lifeless matter. It contradicts the theory of biogenesis in science. This teaching that man came from inanimate matter, is a mere theory, not scientific fact; and it is a theory greatly lacking in real evidence. The language of Genesis 1:26 reveals that man is not a product of evolution, but a new creation, different from all that was created before³⁰. Truth cannot be subverted or suppressed because we can do nothing against it (2 Cor 13:8). Both the big bang theory and Darwinism are in sharp contrast to the biblical cosmogony.

That God exists and created all things, including man, is very obvious to us. What can be known of God and His creation is evident. No one can deny it except the ungodly, the unrighteous, and the foolish whose heart has been darkened:

¹⁷ For therein is the righteousness of God revealed from faith to faith: as it is written, The just shall live by faith. ¹⁸ For the wrath of God is revealed from heaven against all ungodliness and unrighteousness of men, who hold the truth in unrighteousness; ¹⁹ Because that which may be known of God is manifest in them; for God hath shewed it unto them. {in them: or, to them} ²⁰ For the invisible things of him from the creation of the world are clearly seen, being understood by the things that are made, even his eternal power and Godhead; so that they are without excuse: {so...: or, that they may be} ²¹ Because that, when they knew God, they glorified him not as God, neither were thankful; but became vain in their imaginations, and their foolish heart was darkened (Rom 1: 17-21).

The Bible asserts, God Himself makes it known, severally that the universe and everything in it belong to God who created them (Exo 19:5; 20:11; Deut 10:14; 1Chron 29:11; Job 41:11; Ps 24:1; 50:10-12; 89:11; 1Cor 10:26; etc).

²⁹ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Adam_\(given_name\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Adam_(given_name))

³⁰ For a better understanding, see “Pastors English Study Bible”

The Creation Account of Man:

1. Genesis 1:26-27: God creates man (Adam) in His own image (Imago Dei) and not in the image of gorilla or apes or any animal. God Created man to have dominion over His creation, including all the animals (Gen 1:28).
2. Genesis 2:7: God forms Adam from the dust of the ground and not by mutation or natural selection.
3. Genesis 2:22: God creates Eve from Adam's rib and not evolution
4. Man has one origin (Monogenesis): All humans descended from Adam – from one blood (Acts 17:26).
5. Man is a special being: The method God used to create man is unique and different from that of animals. God created man, His image, from the dust of the ground and animated man's image by His Spirit to make man a living soul (Gen 1:1-25, 26-27; 2:7; Job 27:3; 32:8; 33:4).
6. God created man as a mature being – fully formed. Man did not evolve from any matter.
7. Man (Adam) gave names to all the animals (Gen 2:19-20)

The Tripartite Man

In 1Thessalonians 5: 23, the Bible says unequivocally that: “And the very God of peace sanctify you wholly; and I pray God your whole spirit and soul and body be preserved blameless unto the coming of our Lord Jesus Christ” (Emphasis mine). The figures 1 to 3 illustrate how each element of man's composition interrelated.

Fig 1: The difference between Body, Soul, and Spirit

Fig 2: The Tripartite Man (Trichotomy of Man)

Man is a spirit, he has a soul but lives in a body.

Fig 3: The Tripartite Man: the spirit, soul, and body have their separate functions yet interconnected. The three are all important.

The Tripartite Man, also known as the Trichotomy of Man, is a biblical concept describing the three distinct aspects of human nature. This Trinitarian composition of man describes man as consisting of three distinct but interconnected parts:

1. Body (Physical) (Soma):

- The physical body, made up of flesh and blood (1 Corinthians 15:50)
- Subject to temptation, weakness, and decay (Romans 6:12, 8:10; 1Cor 15:42-44)
- Formed out of clay (Job 33:6)
- Will return to dust after death (Genesis 3:19; Eccl 12: 7)

2. Soul (Emotional/Relational) (Psyche):

- The seat of emotions, desires, personality and intellectual aspect (Psalm 42:11, 1 Peter 2:11)
- Experiences emotions like joy, sorrow, and love (John 11:35, 1 John 4:8)
- Connects with others through relationships (Genesis 2:24, Ephesians 5:28-31)

3. Spirit (Spiritual) (Pneuma):

- The breath of life, imparting spiritual life (Genesis 2:7, John 20:22)
- Communes with God, enabling faith and worship (Romans 8:16, 1 Corinthians 6:17)
- Longs for fellowship with God and eternal life (Psalm 42:2, 2 Corinthians 5:8; John 4: 24)
- The immaterial, eternal aspect of humanity
- Connects humans to God, enabling spiritual life and communion

Note that this tripartite nature is rooted in Scripture:

- 1 Thessalonians 5:23: "May your whole spirit, soul, and body be preserved blameless..."
- Hebrews 4:12: "Dividing soul and spirit, joints and marrow."

Interactions between the Three Parts:

- Body and Soul: Physical experiences affect emotions and relationships (Proverbs 14:13, 1 Corinthians 7:5)
- Soul and Spirit: Emotions and desires influence spiritual decisions (Psalm 42:11, Romans 8:5-8)
- Body and Spirit: Physical actions can impact spiritual well-being (1 Corinthians 6:19-20, Romans 12:1)

Conclusion

This research study has been able to critically clarify biblical cosmogony through *Theogenesial Theory* that God is the Creator of the universe – all species were created by Him. The paper explains how God created the universe in six days through the power of His spoken words. He spoke the universe into existence by fiat. The creation of the universe was done ex nihilo (out of nothing) as against the big bang theory of a condensed lifeless matter into a singularity that culminated in sudden explosion arising from a generated heat. It also contradicts Darwinism, the scientific theory of evolution through natural selection, proposed by Charles Darwin in his popular book, *On the Origin of Species*, in 1859. The theory states that all living organisms evolve over time through the process of variation, mutation, genetic drift, and gene flow, with the primary driving force being natural selection. The paper subsequently elucidates the tripartite nature of man created by God in His image (Imago Dei) that man was created by God out of the dust of the ground, and God imparted on the body of man through his nostril His breath of life to produce a living soul. Thus, the study sets a *Demarcation Standard for Truth (DST)* to evaluate the reliability of claims to truth, which Darwinism and other associated theories on the origin of the universe could not meet.

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